

```

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from imblearn.over_sampling import SMOTE
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

# Load your credit card fraud dataset (replace 'creditcard.csv' with your dataset file)
df = pd.read_csv('/kaggle/input/creditcardfraud/creditcard.csv')

# Split the dataset into features (X) and target (y)
X = df.drop('Class', axis=1)
y = df['Class']

# Split the data into a single train-test split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Standardize features (important for some algorithms)
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test = scaler.transform(X_test)

# Apply SMOTE to oversample the minority class
smote = SMOTE(random_state=42)
X_train_resampled, y_train_resampled = smote.fit_resample(X_train, y_train)

# Check the class distribution before and after SMOTE
print("Class distribution before SMOTE:")
print(y_train.value_counts())
print("\nClass distribution after SMOTE:")
print(pd.Series(y_train_resampled).value_counts())

# Calculate total number and percentage
total_before_smote = len(y_train)
total_after_smote = len(y_train_resampled)
percentage_before_smote = y_train.value_counts() / total_before_smote * 100
percentage_after_smote = pd.Series(y_train_resampled).value_counts() / total_after_smote * 100

# Plot the data distribution before and after SMOTE
plt.figure(figsize=(14, 6))
plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)
sns.countplot(x=y_train, palette='Set2')
plt.title(f"Class Distribution Before SMOTE\nTotal: {total_before_smote}\n{percentage_before_smote[0]:.2f}% Non-Fraud | {percentage_before_smote[1]:.2f}% Fraud")

plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)
sns.countplot(x=y_train_resampled, palette='Set2')
plt.title(f"Class Distribution After SMOTE\nTotal: {total_after_smote}\n{percentage_after_smote[0]:.2f}% Non-Fraud | {percentage_after_smote[1]:.2f}% Fraud")

plt.tight_layout()

```

```
plt.show()
```

```
# Save a copy of the SMOTE oversampled dataset
```

```
smote_oversampled_df = pd.DataFrame(X_train_resampled, columns=X.columns)
```

```
smote_oversampled_df['Class'] = y_train_resampled
```

```
smote_oversampled_df.to_csv('/kaggle/working/creditcard_smote_oversampled.csv', index=False)
```

Class distribution before SMOTE:

Class

0 227451

1 394

Name: count, dtype: int64

Class distribution after SMOTE:

Class

0 227451

1 227451

Name: count, dtype: int64

add Codeadd Markdown


```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.linear_model import LogisticRegression
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsClassifier
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import (
    accuracy_score,
    precision_score,
    recall_score,
    f1_score,
    roc_auc_score,
    roc_curve,
```

```

    confusion_matrix,
)
import time
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns

# Load your credit card fraud dataset (replace 'creditcard.csv' with your dataset file)
df = pd.read_csv('creditcard_smote_oversampled.csv')

# Split the dataset into features (X) and target (y)
X = df.drop('Class', axis=1)
y = df['Class']

# Split the data into a single train-test split
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Standardize features (important for some algorithms)
scaler = StandardScaler()
X_train = scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
X_test = scaler.transform(X_test)

# Initialize classifiers
classifiers = {
    'SVM': SVC(probability=True), # Note: Set probability=True for ROC AUC calculation
    'Logistic Regression': LogisticRegression(),
    'K-Nearest Neighbors': KNeighborsClassifier(),
    'Gaussian Naive Bayes': GaussianNB(),
    'Random Forest': RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42)
}

# Initialize an empty list to store the dictionaries of metrics for each classifier
metrics_list = []

# Evaluate each classifier on the single train-test split
for name, clf in classifiers.items():
    print(f"Classifier: {name}")

    # Record start time for evaluation
    start_time = time.time()

    try:
        clf.fit(X_train, y_train)
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"Error occurred while fitting {name}: {str(e)}")
        continue

    # Predict on the test set
    y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)

    # Calculate evaluation metrics
    accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
    precision = precision_score(y_test, y_pred)
    recall = recall_score(y_test, y_pred)
    f1 = f1_score(y_test, y_pred)

```

```

# Predict probabilities for positive class (fraud)
y_prob = clf.predict_proba(X_test)[: , 1]

# Calculate ROC AUC
roc_auc = roc_auc_score(y_test, y_prob)

# Record end time for evaluation
end_time = time.time()

# Calculate execution time
execution_time = end_time - start_time

# Append metrics to the list
metrics_list.append({
    'Classifier': name,
    'Accuracy': accuracy,
    'Precision': precision,
    'Recall': recall,
    'F1 Score': f1,
    'ROC AUC': roc_auc
})

# Print metrics for each classifier
print(f"Execution Time: {execution_time:.2f} seconds")
print(f"Accuracy: {accuracy}")
print(f"Precision: {precision}")
print(f"Recall: {recall}")
print(f"F1 Score: {f1}")
print(f"ROC AUC: {roc_auc}")
print("=" * 50)

# Plot the confusion matrix
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
cm = confusion_matrix(y_test, y_pred)
sns.heatmap(cm, annot=True, fmt='d', cmap='Blues', cbar=False)
plt.title(f"Confusion Matrix for {name}")
plt.xlabel("Predicted")
plt.ylabel("Actual")
plt.show()

# Plot ROC AUC curve
fpr, tpr, _ = roc_curve(y_test, y_prob)
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 6))
plt.plot(fpr, tpr, label=f"{name} (AUC = {roc_auc:.2f})")
plt.plot([0, 1], [0, 1], linestyle='--', color='gray')
plt.xlabel("False Positive Rate")
plt.ylabel("True Positive Rate")
plt.title(f"ROC Curve for {name}")
plt.legend(loc='lower right')
plt.show()

# Create a DataFrame from the list of metrics
metrics_df = pd.DataFrame(metrics_list)

# Print the metrics DataFrame

```

```
print("\nPerformance Metrics for Classifiers:")  
print(metrics_df)
```

```
Classifier: SVM  
Execution Time: 6936.48 seconds  
Accuracy: 0.993789912179466  
Precision: 0.9925167388735723  
Recall: 0.9951078252857425  
F1 Score: 0.9938105931971299  
ROC AUC: 0.9997443254702709  
=====
```

Confusion Matrix for SVM

Classifier: Logistic Regression
Execution Time: 5.68 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9493520625185479
Precision: 0.9759553955163202
Recall: 0.9216155145558651
F1 Score: 0.9480074017240603
ROC AUC: 0.9906659247287267

=====

Confusion Matrix for Logistic Regression

Classifier: K-N

Nearest Neighbors
Execution Time: 192.07 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9982633736714259
Precision: 0.9965457685664939
Recall: 1.0
F1 Score: 0.9982698961937717
ROC AUC: 0.9994713423498833
=====

Confusion Matrix for K-Nearest Neighbors

Classifier: Gaussian Naive Bayes
Execution Time: 0.38 seconds
Accuracy: 0.9136083358063771
Precision: 0.9742525961127455
Recall: 0.8500318101046442
F1 Score: 0.9079129273379104
ROC AUC: 0.9500747428803251

=====

Classifier: Random Forest
Execution Time: 443.88 seconds

Accuracy: 0.9999230608588606
Precision: 0.9998464575564817
Recall: 1.0
F1 Score: 0.9999232228839678
ROC AUC: 0.9999882198847289

=====

Confusion Matrix for Random Forest

ROC Curve for Random Forest

